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Innovative pedagogical experiences at Basque Country inclusive schools

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Abstract

In this study, we present the experiences of three educational projects with over thirty years of pedagogical innovation in the Basque Country: “The Amara Berri System”, “Eskola Txikiak” and “The Antzuola Project”. These include innovations with an inclusive focus as well as practices that affect the curriculum and school organisation for the purpose of satisfying community demands and fulfilling objectives related to diversity and school well-being. The results obtained in the fieldwork have encouraged us to think

about how barriers such as curriculum and school organization can be overcome through educational projects that cater to the diversity and needs of the educational community.

Key words: Inclusive school; pedagogical innovation; curriculum; school well-being; school organization.

Introduction

The concept of an inclusive school follows the line of thinking that sees education as a basic human right, a social option that reclaims the right to quality education for all (Ainscow, 2016; Ainscow and Messiou, 2018; Arnáiz, 2003; Parrilla, 2007). Inclusive schools are those that overcome all forms of discrimination and educational exclusion. Ainscow et al. (2006a) and Echeíta (2006) define them as schools that guarantee that all boys, girls and youth have access to a quality education. As presented by Booth and Ainscow (2005), an inclusive school requires a transformational approach with a series of implications focused on the following: the creation of inclusive cultures, preparation of inclusive policies, and development of inclusive practises. According to these same authors, inclusion is an indicator, or quality factor, because it implies a guaranteed right to education for all students. The creation of inclusive schools is based on two fundamental aspects: the establishment of inclusive values, and the creation of an educational community (López Melero, 2011). In such a community, students experience a feeling of ‘belonging’ to the school. The school is a community, an organised context that provides a welcoming and rich experience, where everyone is known, recognised and treated as such, and where everyone participates directly in the school’s activities. These features are essential in offering each member of the school community the necessary well-being, and encouraging participation, motivation and creativity in each individual (Arguiñano et al., 2018; Karrera et al., 2019).

However, this new paradigm requires rethinking our educational perspective. The knowledge society has brought about a change in the learning model. Nowadays, knowledge is presented not as something static, but as a dynamic entity, largely volatile, along with the demands of a society that needs competent individuals who know how to work in teams. All of this requires a profound shift in educational practice and school organisation. We refer to practices that give students the authority to enquire, coordinate and articulate the ways in which they access knowledge or engage in problem resolution. It is necessary to address these new challenges with more extensive development of emerging educational practices capable of meeting the needs of today's society.

Given this situation, different authors have affirmed that pedagogical innovation is a useful tool that can be utilised by the educational system to meet society's needs (Cabero, 2007; Carbonell, 2002; Cárdenas, 1999; Deal, 1990; Díaz-Aguado et al., 2004; Imbernón, 1996; Martinic, 2001; Pascual, 1988; Sancho and Correa, 2013). Educational innovation is an instrument that can help overcome the situation of inertia and passiveness created by the needs of industrial society and the mechanical practices that have arisen in its wake. Moreover, Carbonell (2002) describes it as a process of systemised ideas and strategies to create a change in educational practise, and offers factors that can change life in the classroom, a centre's organisation, community dynamics, and the educator's teaching culture. On the other hand, Duarte Hueros (2000) uses the definitions given by Escudero (1995) and Kemmis (1994), and defines educational innovation as follows: 'Although this term has multiple meanings according to the literature reviewed, we are referring to a process of change that aims to introduce new elements with the goal of improvement' (Duarte Hueros, 2000, p. 131). This implies a critical and reflective attitude (Escudero, 1995), the purpose of which is to improve the condition of subjects and social progress (Kemmis, 1994).

Therefore, educational innovation must change traditional learning with a transfer of knowledge for a different type of schooling, the purpose of which is to endow students with the creativity necessary to generate knowledge, and to train them to put that knowledge into practise. In other words, the objective is to provide learning that seeks to promote a discerning attitude and teamwork, contributes to self-awareness and community consciousness, promotes a feeling of fairness, and encourages the mere right to exist.

New challenges

There is no doubt that schools are making great efforts to promote quality education for all, but as Krichesky and Murillo (2011), Hopkins (2007) and Fullam (2002) point out, for one reason or another the pedagogical innovations that many schools have implemented in order to adapt their educational projects to the new paradigm have failed to achieve this goal.

One of the barriers hindering this work can be found in the Educational Project of the Centres themselves. In order to improve the quality of centres, school administrators have proposed changes aimed at improving the dynamics of the classroom. However, this is something that rarely manages to improve the quality of a school. As Stoll et al. (2006) have stated, in order for projects to have a greater probability of offering improvement, they must be aimed at reinventing the school culture.

Another barrier to generating an educational project capable of responding to all of the diversity in the classroom is the curriculum itself, according to Blanco (2014), Valencia Pérez and Hernández González (2017), Alba et al. (2014), and Booth et al. (2015). The purpose of a school is to transmit knowledge, values and skills from one generation to another (McCulloch, 2004).

In order to improve and standardize the processes of teaching and learning and homogenize the knowledge transmitted in schools, general curricula began to be developed. However, even the standardization and homogenization that a curriculum has exercised in designing, grouping, or evaluating may become an important barrier from the moment that a classroom becomes non-homogeneous (Ainscow and West, 2008; Florian, 2014).

In an attempt to overcome these obstacles, we present in this study the pedagogical experiences arising from innovative work carried out over the past 30 years at forward-thinking public schools in the Basque Country during the nursery and primary school stages. We present three different educational projects: ‘The Amara Berri System’, ‘Eskola Txikiak’ and ‘The Antzuola Project’, all of which have been selected by the Department of Education of the Basque Government as benchmark centres in educational innovation.

These educational projects are different from one another, but their view of education converges on important aspects, such as the following: the values reflected in their Educational Centre Project, the pedagogical innovations carried out at the time of implementing the curriculum, the adaptations made in their school organization, and/or their close relationship with the community where they are located.

Research design

The design of this research was based on a collaborative study (Carr and Kemmis, 1988; Kemmis, 2012), seen as a variant of the ethnographic method (Woods, 1987), and yet directly related to it. This method is oriented to qualitative methodological research, which is precisely why we decided to use it. Thanks to the method and to the methodology, we were able to discover and describe in depth what occurs at Nursery and

Primary schools; in fact, we had access to this restricted context, which is why we were able to recognise and clarify tasks and attitudes of people who interact therein on a daily basis.

Furthermore, we were interested in identifying the practices and behaviours beforehand, so we opened up an enquiry period for different topics among all group members. In later meetings, points of interest were provisionally marked. Later, thanks to the information collected during the observation sessions, these issues were ultimately classified as follows: Autonomy, Communication, Curriculum Design, School Organization, Motivation, Conflict Resolution, Group Work, Student Tasks in Relation to the Curriculum, Evaluation, Teacher Functions/Training, and Interaction with the Community. However, for reasons of space limitations, we have decided to present the results of the analysis in a descriptive way, emphasizing the aspects collected in the different categories.

The techniques used for information collection and analysis were as follows:

- Documentation review. Following the recommendations of Woods (1989), publications made by the different teaching teams of the centres, internal documentation, and educational planning have been revised.
- Observation sessions: The techniques used to collect information included a series of participant observation sessions conducted at the educational centres. Twelve observation sessions were carried out, each lasting 4 hours. A register of the information was created using field notes collected in both a narrative and categorical way.
- Interviews: Three communicative interviews were conducted, one with each administrative management team. These interviews were recorded and

transcribed. This made it easier to categorize the information collected and to codify it for later analysis.

- Focus groups: In order to reach the data saturation point and find answers to the emerging categories that arose during the interviews, a discussion group was held with the pedagogical leaders of the centres.

The analysis techniques used were content analysis and information triangulation (Karrera, 2008; Pérez Serrano, 2008). Once a content analysis was carried out regarding the observations, interviews, and discussion groups for contrasting the information, observing it from different perspectives, and validating the data, the information was triangulated according to the triangulation types indicated by Reimers (2000).

Once the information was analysed and the document was prepared, it was provided to the main participants for verification, and if necessary, for the purpose of complementing and/or correcting all aspects they deemed pertinent. All of this had a two-fold purpose: one was to guarantee the ‘confirmation criteria’ (Del Rincón et al., 1995), by offering the document to participants for verification. The other was to build spaces for comprehension, consensus and cooperation among all individuals linked to the research.

This work was carried out in compliance with the parameters established by the ethics committee (*CEISH* in Spanish). In addition, it was ensured that this research would be conducted with respect for the freedoms and rights of all participants without excluding anyone. As required by the ethics committee, the welfare of individuals was placed above the interests of this study.

Results

The educational projects described in the section below are those that changed the way the centres operate, and the way they view education as well. They were all selected by the Department of Education of the Basque Government as benchmark centres in educational innovation. These projects include, ‘The Amara Berri System’, ‘Eskola Txikiak’ and ‘The Antzuola Project’. The first two, Amara Berri and Eskola Txikiak, are networks of schools. We have collected information from two schools from each network. Antzuola is a different case; it is a single school that has created and developed its own particular educational project.

The Amara Berri System

In the Amara Berri System, the primary school classroom is called a ‘department’, which is organised according to different learning contexts (spaces and tasks). As one of the founders of the Amara Berri system points out, games are the basis, or essence, of these contexts. It is not a question of motivation, as each person has his or her own motives. The key is for the games to connect with pupils’ interests and allow them to flourish. In every game, along with a certain amount of effort required, there is also a feeling of wellbeing and satisfaction in overcoming challenges.

These are not competitive games, but endeavours of collaboration, and taking into account that the pupils imitate the adult world, teachers design the game-activity (context) as a didactic exercise that allows students to learn by doing: ‘I don’t learn numbers to be able to shop. I shop, and by shopping, I learn numbers’ (Anaut, 2004, p. 253).

Within these departments, students are grouped by cycles, not by school year; in other words, students of different ages interact in the departments. This grouping style began

even before the General Educational System Regulation Act (*Ley de Ordenación General del Sistema Educativo-LOGSE*) was established in 1990.

These centres, such as "EskolaTxikiak" and "Antzuola" (the experiences of which we will introduce later), believe that diversity is an important characteristic in human beings and that a difference in age is a pedagogical resource that makes it possible to achieve even further enrichment of the learning process. "Differences are considered a quality, not a discriminating factor" (García et al., 2011, p. 264).

Grouping students by cycles offers them new references, as some have been in the department for a year, while others are just starting out:

Due to their lack of awareness of the new system, those who arrive to the program for the first time ask the older students questions, and the latter assume the role of teacher, helping their peers by using a language that is more familiar to the new students. The fact of answering the younger students' questions enables the restructuring of their ideas and the consolidation of their knowledge (Anaut, 2004, p. 94).

Within learning contexts, or in other words, within one same department, different areas where students develop various subjects and/or tasks are organised. Throughout the school year, girls and boys rotate in and out of all the departments and contexts. Each department has a foundation of what we know as a 'subject', but this is within a context that brings the student closer to a specific reality, while at the same time providing for the development of different skills. For example, in the first Primary Education cycle within the neighbourhood department, hands-on contexts predominate, where we find the following: a living room, kitchen, sewing room, and a shop.

We observe that due to the symbolism created by the daily experiences developed by citizens in the neighbourhood, operational contexts predominate. Within these contexts,

students engage in experiences such as selling products or handling coins, as well as tasks related to the home, etc. On one hand, the aim is to make the transition from the Nursery phase to the Primary phase occur gradually, while at the same time working on mathematics, communication and social skills. Within the departments, the only didactic materials available to students are those that can be managed independently.

Another striking aspect in the daily life of the school is the way that students transition from one task to the next, which occurs progressively. There are no bells or abrupt calls to attention that force students to finish their work instantaneously. Instead, teachers tell students they must begin finishing the task in which they are engaged, and then students wait until the job is finished so they can join a different task or department in an independent and unhurried manner.

In a traditional system, teachers might argue that they get to know students better by spending more time with them in the classroom. In general, this might be a teacher's perspective. Even so, a new school organisation that re-groups students in a more diverse way based on their plurality becomes a pedagogical resource to satisfy the need for diversity in an improved way. With regard to teachers, we were told the following: 'If we share students, whether you like it or not, we are forced to share ideas and practises, because the very school structure forces us to share. The organisational structure itself becomes an intervention strategy' (E/AB.002220). Such an organisation forces teachers to share tutorials. For this reason, 'the educational project is a process of personal and group development for the entire educational community, not just for students' (E/AB.005510).

Amara Berri is not a method, but a system, so new elements can be added as they emerge in society. Students are unbound individuals with their own motivations and interests, with a determined conceptual and emotional make-up, and with their own

individual potential. According to the Amara Berri System (Anaut, 2004), this method of working allows the principles governing their system to become established and to develop within the department itself. These principles are as follows: individualisation, socialisation, creativity, freedom, globalisation and normalization. Each department has a bond with the real world, so each department takes on a social component.

Scheduling activities and organizing the workflows of each project are closely related to stable, complementary social contexts in which didactic tasks are conducted by students on a daily basis. These tasks culminate in radio programmes, TV programmes, or articles that are published in one of the centre's magazines, thus giving the activities 'meaning' and creating the idea that the work has a purpose.

These issues, in addition to having a direct impact on student motivation and their attitude toward schooling, help to strengthen the relationship and communication between the school and the community. Furthermore, in addition to allowing students to share their work, exhibitions help them develop the skills needed to articulate their tasks, thereby allowing them to internalise what they have learned.

With the Amara Berri system, teachers take on a guiding role, allowing students to interact together and to learn from each other. This system of work provides students with a high degree of autonomy, with each student forming part of the process and its timing. In short, students learn to self-regulate their own work.

The Amara Berri system prepares stable learning contexts and offers the opportunity to return to them, thereby encouraging social interaction, ensuring that activities are real, etc. The school organisation forces heterogeneous student grouping. Being a system, new aspects can be introduced therein, and it 'makes the Amara Berri system an organisation that flows and properly overcomes difficulties that all educational organisations must face' (E/AB.011220).

Student evaluation is also part of the Amara Berri educational project. Evaluation is carried out as a continuous process for the purpose of learning, aimed at helping teachers intervene in a different way. This simple issue is something that both teachers and students must understand: evaluation is a natural and necessary action for improvement, and ‘one must feel that the evaluation is not a burden, but an aid’ (E/AB.010736), so it must not be limited to marking, but instead should be a collective process of reflection and assessment.

Eskola Txikiak

In this section, we present the educational project developed by the Eskola Txikiak organization, a network of schools with 40 years of experience in the Basque Country. Each ‘Eskola Txikia’, or rural school, decides on the nuances it deems appropriate for its methodological practise, but obviously, all of the schools are obligated to follow the curriculum established by the public administration. The results set out below have been collected from two schools from this network.

In these educational centres, teachers have made the decision not to group students according to age; this means that children between 3 and 12 years of age cohabit different spaces available at the centre. After being designed by the teaching team, this proposal was presented and agreed upon by family members and the centre’s educational administration. Children from different academic years are mixed in workshops in order to deliberately search for diversity as it exists in society. This is done not only according to age, but to student’s skills and interests as well. These centres have been strengthening Tonucci’s ideological line of thinking over the past four years, immersed in this comprehensive innovation project, modifying both the school and how it works.

With this aim, they have drawn up a Nursery and Primary School curriculum without subjects, age, and/or school-year groupings. Traditional subjects have led to different workshops, such as the following:

- Art workshop, to develop skills of creativity, expressiveness and imagination such as drawing and painting, or the use of clay to make different handicrafts.
- Science workshop, where pupils cultivate their own vegetable garden, carry out culinary activities, and experiment with and investigate nature.
- The Library, where pupils develop their skills in reading, writing, literature, poetry, and more.
- Mathematics workshop, where children perform projects related to construction or robotics. They also play with space, geometry and measurements. In this workshop, they use coloured strips to learn how to count.
- Movement workshop, where students perform activities of psychomotricity, body expression, dance, music and physical activity.

The children are the ones who freely decide which workshops they want to attend, how long they will stay, what project they want to develop, and whether they want to do it alone or in a group.

The teacher takes on the role of acting as someone who aids and accompanies the student in the process, providing the help that he or she needs. Students do not know which school year or level they are in, since they are constantly interacting, working and collaborating with classmates of different ages. During a participatory observation session held by a researcher from this team at one of the schools, a girl was asked what her current school year was. The girl did not know what to say, and referred the question to one of the teachers. The girl was in her third year of primary school.

In one of the conversations held with the educational team at the same school, comments were made regarding the learning process, and why they continue to maintain a few exclusive weekly hours for reading, writing, learning, or subjects such as maths and English. This is somehow related to teacher concerns. How do they respond to the demands of the curriculum? Some teachers find this aspect unnerving. Even more so when they only have few years of experience.

‘We aren’t content-based. We’re based on experiences at the school. During mandatory time slots, we do inter-disciplinary skills, such as developing a love of reading, proper writing, and mastery of mathematics, but it’s because of our own fear. The freer they are, the more things come out! But we’re afraid, and we force them to do those hours. Some of them can spend up to two or three days a week without leaving the art or movement workshop, and that worries us a lot’ (ET/TE.012930).

These schools seek balance between the contemporary pedagogical ideas they have implemented and conventional curricular demands. The team of teachers continuously question themselves, searching and reflecting on how they can confront and overcome the difficulties and/or fears that arise at the school and in their community.

To overcome the community’s fears, teachers hold regular meetings with families. At these gatherings, they reflect on the project and share any doubts that may arise. Training sessions are held every year, which are attended by teachers and the families of students. Teachers strive to achieve a community united around the Educational Project. When a new student arrives at the centre, the rest of the students carry out activities to get to know the family, its background, its origins, and culture. ‘It is the school that must take charge of the issues necessary to promote equality’ (EskTx_1.dok_ez/ref).

Antzuola's Project

The Antzuola Project (hereinafter, Antzuola H.E.) is also worthy of mention as far as innovative educational processes are concerned. Antzuola H.E. has spent more than 30 years strengthening an innovative project and has made an effort to create a new methodological framework based on the community's needs. The most relevant and extensive scientific literature describing the centre's operations narrates different experiences of the educational team, signed by the same team as Antzuola Herri Eskola (Antzuola Herri Eskola, 1999, 2000, 2001a, 2001b; Antzuola Herri Eskola, 2003, 2004a, 2004b; Antzuola Herri Eskola, 2006, 2007, 2008, 2009, 2012, 2014).

The centre's main objective was clear from the beginning: to promote school well-being for all. Moreover, when they say well-being, what they mean is, "when a child gets up in the morning, he or she believes it's worth going to school" (An/ET-2_002827). What the school does is related to what will occur with these boys and girls in the future. Hence, the following observation:

The definitive proof is precisely what the school does so the children experience a positive relationship with knowledge, have a positive perception of themselves, and can reach a high degree of personal well-being (An/dok-4_41).

Therefore, Antzuola H.E. attempts to create contexts for well-being, cooperation, motivation and freedom, where the relationship with knowledge is positive and linked to people, their interactions, interests, concerns, and desire to learn (Sasieta and Etxaniz, 2015). For this reason, they believe the resolution of conflict is essential in cultivating friendly relationships that are established with the people in the school community. Cordial, respectful, empathetic interactions are promoted, which means that great importance is placed on verbal and non-verbal language training.

The concept of the school is to act as a social framework where people with different experiences, thoughts, and ways of viewing the world interact. This makes Antzuola H.E. an enriching context with a learning process that does not provide only right and wrong answers, but rather different ways of viewing reality. It is from this interaction and communication that polyhedral, or three-dimensional knowledge emerges, thereby cohering, creating bonds, and building an inclusive sense of community oriented toward knowledge. To make this interaction between students of different ages a reality, the school keeps its classroom doors open and facilitates student work in different spaces of the centre (building hall, corridors, courtyard, etc.).

A brief example of this pedagogical practice can be found in the work carried out by the pupils in year 4 of primary school. They wanted to know about human inventions throughout history. They agreed to build a Leonardo da Vinci odometer. From a drawing of the Da Vinci odometer, the following questions arose: How does it work? What kind of parts does it have?

Each student wrote a text explaining what they thought it was like, what pieces it was made of, how these worked, how they were connected to each other, etc. This served to increase their commitment to the project. Because of this interaction, the mechanism became specific: 'For every complete turn of the wheel, a marble falls into a box...' Afterward, each student made a cardboard wheel. This material allowed each student to make and present their own wheel.

At that point, the teacher encouraged them by saying: 'You know, we usually have different ideas, and it's important to know everyone's ideas; make the wheel as you like, because you know that with all your ideas we can understand many things'. The sketches of the resulting wheels were highly diverse, and this allowed different problems to emerge regarding their measurement: 'How long does the perimeter measure?' A dialogue was

opened on the properties common to all of the wheels in order to explain in writing the meaning of diameter, radius, perimeter, etc.

Next, they decided that their wheel would have a perimeter of 1.5m and that a marble would fall after each turn. The teacher encouraged them once again by asking, ‘How much do we have to open the compass to make a wheel with a perimeter of 1.5 m?’

In a step-by-step manner, the project was taking shape as everyone found solutions to this and other problems that arose (wheel gears, use of rulers and protractors for measurements, etc.).

While building the wheel that was now in the technology workshop, an infinite number of mathematical actions took place: measuring, looking for distances, drawing parallel lines or different shapes, using three-dimensional material, and so on. Once the odometer was built, the time came to exhibit the machine and explain to others the meaning of everything they had done, reflected on, discovered, experienced, and so on.

The curriculum at Antzuola H.E. is framed within the methodology known as Global Project Based Learning (PBL), where dialogue and communication with and among students is a priority. With this curriculum, there are no specific subjects. Instead, daily educational practise is focused on developing projects that are proposed, developed and shared by the students themselves by means of the democratic process, thus fulfilling PBL’s essential characteristics (Tawfik, 2015). Each work project is unique and unrepeatable, as each group works according to the interests that emerge from its members. Moreover, the didactic design is not rigid, but flexible, providing the opportunity to go more deeply to include new ideas and fields of research that arise throughout the learning process. For this reason, a project’s procedure may deviate from the initial approach depending on the concerns, interests or difficulties experienced by the work group (Sasieta and Etxaniz, 2015).

During the development of the projects, and especially at the end, students make frequent presentations to different audiences to present their work. This activity of continually sharing work projects allows students of different ages to learn from each other, and generates a relationship that begins at the school centre and spreads, acting as a bond between students outside the school and the academic realm. This provides for improved relationships outside the school environment, and thus helps to care for the well-being of individuals in the community.

The main objective of this school is to safeguard the well-being of its students and enable them to engage in life-long learning and to face the challenges of life with a discerning disposition. To achieve this goal, the educational centre selected flexible groups, with students changing groups or creating new ones depending on the needs of the project being carried out. This freedom of movement has allowed teachers to observe and understand the relationships within the group they are leading. This is valuable information that helps to guide and promote a diversity of ideas, characters and relationships emerging in the educational centre, where student groupings act as an additional tool in supporting personal and collective learning.

At Antzuola H.E., teaching authority is used with the aim of empowering students. 'Teachers have decided that the student is the one who must decide' (An/ET-3_004134). This implies a horizontal framework where the entire collective makes decisions from its own perspective.

As stated by Apple and Beane (1997), in a democratic classroom students and teachers collaborate in planning and making decisions that satisfy the concerns, aspirations and interests of both. At Antzuola H.E., this issue is very important. By means of PBL, students are constantly encouraged to make decisions. They decide what subjects they want to use as a basis for carrying out their projects, what they want to learn in the

endeavour, and how they want to do it. With the idea that students have the right to be heard, and that teachers must be willing to listen (Apple and Beane, 1997), the changing of roles is necessary. Teachers become those who formulate the problems and organise knowledge and learning, ceasing to be the ones who teach (Gadotti, 2007). To this end, they take into account two very important and inseparable issues: how the students learn, and how they feel. This is the teacher's task. They try to provide access to knowledge for members of the group, in addition to inducing well-being and culture, because teachers know that students will not achieve knowledge if they do not have well-being. On the other hand, students become active participants in their own learning process, acting as the core of this dynamic process, and they adapt projects to the decisions that they themselves make.

Discussion

Inclusion means believing in the capabilities of students, teachers and families. It means creating and sharing spaces for learning, working and discovering together. It means inspiring schools to create an atmosphere in which each individual feels like part of an educational community that moves forward and welcomes each other. Inclusion means taking every student into account, offering time and space to learn the opinion and mood of community members, caring about each student, teacher and other participants in the educational community, and feeling valued and important to the community. Educational inclusion demands collaboration and cooperation among people in order to learn from mistakes (Schulz, 2010); in fact, mistakes should be seen as true learning opportunities (Ainscow et al., 2006b). We must not forget that we come to school to learn, so making mistakes is natural; moreover, making mistakes at school is necessary for learning.

Developing an inclusive school requires redefining the roles and tasks of all members of the educational community, profoundly transforming vital areas such as curriculum and structure. These transformations should be seen not only from the perspective of the principles and values set forth in the Centre's Educational Project, but more importantly from the point of view of the organisation of the centre itself, its didactic process, curricular organisation, harmonious cohabitation, school atmosphere, how relations are conducted, the language used, and in the unwritten rules and/or protocols for taking action and addressing or resolving conflicts.

Even though the experiences gathered for this study come from schools belonging to different educational networks (Amara Berri System, Eskola Txikiak, and Antzuola H.E.), the centres we have included are highlighted by principles and actions that can help us move toward a more inclusive school, in our opinion. Some of these principles and actions include the following:

1) Centre Project:

- a) The centres believe that their Educational Project is framed within the comprehensive construction of an inclusive community and society.
- b) They design an Educational Project to attend to the diversity of all students.

2) Curriculum and School Organisation:

- a) They adapt their school organisation to the needs of the emerging curriculum. The learning space is the community, not the classroom. This forces one to rethink and reorganise spaces and groups both inside and outside the educational centre.
- b) They design flexible didactic experiences with inter-disciplinary and comprehensive work Projects and/or Workshops, instead of organising the curriculum based on course subjects.

- c) They offer voluntary student groupings. Students can freely move around the workshops, circuits and/or projects, based on their interests and needs.
- d) Evaluation is a joint process geared toward achieving the required skills. The techniques used in the observation process and the information triangulation and/or application of evaluation models include the concept of "situation-problem" (Perrenoud, 2011; Zabala and Arnau, 2007).

3) Regarding the educational community:

- a) This includes cohabitation in a welcoming, collaborative and stimulating community for learning, where school well-being for everyone is priority.
- b) Students are the cornerstone of learning. Their contributions, whatever they may be, are important, so students feel important. Time is set aside to conduct several activities with the aim of deepening knowledge and recognition among people.
- c) Teachers guide the learning process and act as a support in helping students overcome difficulties arising from the learning and socialisation process.

These aspects are not necessarily valid only for these schools, as they may be of great help for any teaching team interested in moving toward a more inclusive educational project.

In short, an inclusive school is a reflective community that promotes pedagogical innovation as a valid educational approach in moving forward in improving life and school well-being for all persons within the educational community.

Over the past few years, most educational systems have made huge efforts to meet the needs and demands of 21st century society. In this study, we have sought to present Educational Projects in which teachers who accept inclusive doctrines have adapted both their educational practices and their school organisation to these ideas in order to provide

a better response to the demands of the community, student diversity, and student well-being. To achieve this goal, they have implemented educational innovative processes, sought the involvement of the local community itself (local administration, family members and services available in each municipality or region), as well as others outside the community (professionals from different fields, universities and support networks), in order to contextualise their educational proposal and imbue their role of teachers with much greater meaning.

We are of the opinion that pedagogical innovation can begin with moments of reflection and contrasting ideas, but this will eventually give way to an Educational Project that is intimately bound a Centre's Curricular Proposal. Once agreement is reached regarding these two endeavours, a school organisation can be established according to the needs arising from the educational and curricular projects. Various difficulties might arise from this process, both structural (needing to comply with established curriculum, external centre evaluations, requirements and administrative demands, etc.), as well as personal challenges (lack of training, insecurity among teachers regarding new, unforeseen situations, the need for greater coordination and teamwork, etc.). However, one thing is clear. If teachers want this, and consider it important, pedagogical renovation can be pushed forward no matter how many difficulties are encountered" (E/AB.012045). All around us, we find valid references that can help us in this effort.

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References

- Ainscow, M. (2016). Collaboration as a strategy for promoting equity in education: possibilities and barriers. *Journal of Professional capital and community*, 1(2), 159-172. [doi: 10.1108/1220150013](https://doi.org/10.1108/1220150013)
- Ainscow, M., Booth, T., and Dyson, A. (2006a). Inclusion and the standards agenda: negotiating policy pressures in England. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 10(4-5), 295-308. doi:10.1080/13603110500430633
- Ainscow, M., Booth, T., and Dyson, A. (2006b). *Improving Schools, Developing Inclusion*. London, England: Routledge. [doi: 10.4324/9780203967157](https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203967157)

- Ainscow, M., and Messiou, K. (2018). Engaging with the views of students to promote inclusion in education. *Journal of Educational Change*, 19(1), 1-17. doi: 10.1007/1083301793121
- Ainscow, M. and West, M. (2008). *Mejorar las escuelas urbanas*. Madrid. Narcea.
- Alba, C., Sánchez, J., and Zubillaga, A. (2014). Diseño Universal para el aprendizaje. Pautas para su introducción en el currículo. Retrieved from: http://www.educadua.es/doc/dua/dua_pautas_intro_cv.pdf
- Anaut, L. (2004). *Sobre el Sistema Amara Berri*. Vitoria-Gasteiz, Spain: Servicio de Publicaciones del Gobierno Vasco/Eusko Jaurlaritzaren Argitalpen Zerbitzu Nagusia. Retrieved from http://www.hezkuntza.ejgv.euskadi.eus/r43-573/es/contenidos/informacion/dia6/es_2027/adjuntos/Iniciativas%20educativas/Amara%20Berri/Castellano.pdf
- Antzuola Herri Eskola. (1999). Infantil y Primaria ¿Dos mundos independientes? *Cuadernos de Pedagogía*, 282, 40-44.
- Antzuola Herri Eskola. (2000). Gestión del Currículum y concepciones del alumnado. *Cuadernos de Pedagogía*, 290, 70-73.
- Antzuola Herri Eskola. (2001a). El qué, cuándo, para qué... de las matemáticas. *Aula de Innovación Educativa*, 10(103), 20-24.
- Antzuola Herri Eskola. (2001b). Niños y niñas investigadoras: ¿de qué hablamos?. *Aula de infantil*, 1, 17-14.
- Antzuola Herri Eskola. (2003). La cantidad y.. ¡cantidad de significados! *Aula de infantil*, 13, 6-8.
- Antzuola Herri Eskola. (2004a). En la escuela, lo que digo yo también es importante. *Aula de Innovación Educativa*, 132, 41-46.

- Antzuola Herri Eskola. (2004b). Una comunidad que acaba. *Aula de Innovación Educativa*, 132, 40-46.
- Antzuola Herri Eskola. (2006). El Viaje a Marte. *Cuadernos de Pedagogía*, 355, 55-58.
- Antzuola Herri Eskola. (2007). El punto de vista crítico. In M.S. Costanzi, X.A. Morera, A.R., Muxarta, and D.V. Murillo (Eds.) *III. Jornades Estatals. La Cultura Matemática de les Persones. Una Comunidad Orientada a la Comprensión del Mundo* (pp. 54) Barcelona, Spain: UAB. Retrieved from [https://www.uab.cat/doc/VI Jornades Estatals Cultura Matematica Persona](https://www.uab.cat/doc/VI_Jornades_Estatales_Cultura_Matematica_Persona)
[s](#)
- Antzuola Herri Eskola. (2008). Experiències primària: Un claustre que indaga i aprèn com a comunicat. L'escola d'Antzuola. *Perspectiva escolar*, 323, 27-31.
- Antzuola Herri Eskola. (2009). Utilizar Sistemas Para Representar el Mundo. *IV Jornades Estatals. La Cultura Matemàtica de les Persones. Enseñar a Participar en una Conversación Cultural*. Barcelona, Spain. Retrieved from <http://documentsice.uab.cat/IVJornadesMates/index.htm>.
- Antzuola Herri Eskola. (2012). Mi cabeza me dice. *V Jornades estatals. La Cultura Matemàtica de les Persones. Haciendo Posible una Escuela Emancipadora y Orientada al Significado*, Barcelona, Spain. Retrieved from <http://pagines.uab.cat/ice-culturamatematicapersones/content/v-jornades>.
- Antzuola Herri Eskola. (2014). La escuela de Antzuola: las personas y sus interacciones en contextos de aprendizaje inclusivos. *XXI Encuentro de Consejos Escolares Autonómicos y del Estado* (pp. 302-311) Oviedo, Spain. Retrieved from http://www.mecd.gob.es/dctm/cee/encuentros/xxiencuentro/22encuentroceaye_documento_final_jpa.pdf?documentId=0901e72b8194fe50.

- Apple, M. W., and Beane, J. A. (1997). *Escuelas democráticas* (1st ed.). Madrid, Spain: Morata.
- Arguiñano, A., Karrera, I., and Arandia, M. (2018). Funcionamiento democrático y ABP: Factores determinantes para la inclusión y el rendimiento del alumnado. *Revista Electrónica de Investigación Educativa*, 20(2), 103-112. doi: 10.243202018.20.2.1450
- Arnáiz, P. (2003). *Educación inclusiva: una escuela para todos*. Málaga, Spain: Aljibe.
- Blanco, R. (2014). *Inclusión educativa en América Latina: caminos recorridos y por recorrer. Avances y desafíos de la inclusión educativa en Iberoamérica*. España: Organizaciòn de Estados Iberoamericanos para la Educación, la Ciencia y la cultura.
- Booth, T., and Ainscow, M. (2005). *Guía para la evaluación y mejora de la educación inclusiva: desarrollando el aprendizaje y la participación en las escuelas*. Vitoria-Gasteiz, Spain: Servicio de Publicaciones del Gobierno Vasco.
- Booth, T., Simón, C., Sandoval, M., Echeíta, G., and Muñoz, Y. (2015). Guía para la Educación Inclusiva. Promoviendo el Aprendizaje y la Participación en las Escuelas: Nueva Edición Revisada y Ampliada. *REICE. Revista Iberoamericana sobre Calidad, Eficacia y Cambio en Educación*, 13(3), 5-19.
- Cabero, J. (2007). *Nuevas tecnologías aplicadas a la educación*. Madrid, Spain: McGraw-Hill.
- Carbonell, J. (2002). El profesorado y la innovación educativa. In P, Cañan de Leon (Ed.), *Innovación educativa* (pp. 11-26). Madrid, Spain: AKAL.
- Cárdenas, E. J. (1999). *La mediación en conflictos familiares: lo que hay que saber*. Buenos Aires, Argentina: Lumen humanitas.

- Carr, W., and Kemmis, S. (1988). *Teoría crítica de la enseñanza. La investigación-acción en la formación del profesorado*. Barcelona, Spain: Martínez Roca.
- Deal, T. E. (1990). Reframing reform. *Educational leadership*, 47(8), 7-12.
- Del Rincón, D., Arnal, J., Latorre, A., and Sans, A. (1995). *Técnicas de investigación en Ciencias Sociales*. Madrid, Spain: Dykinson.
- Díaz-Aguado, M. J., Martínez-Arias, R. M., and Martín-Seoane, G. M. (2004). *Prevención de la violencia y lucha contra la exclusión desde la adolescencia: la violencia entre iguales en la escuela y el ocio. Estudios comparativos e instrumentos de evaluación*. Madrid, Spain: Instituto de la Juventud.
- Duarte Hueros, A. M. (2000). Innovaciones y nuevas tecnologías: Implicaciones para un cambio educativo. *XXI Revista de Educación*, 2, 129-145.
- Echeíta, G. (2006). *Educación para la inclusión. Educación sin exclusiones*. Madrid: Narcea.
- Escudero, J. M. (1995). La integración de las nuevas tecnologías en el curriculum y en el sistema escolar. In J.L. Rodríguez-Diéguez and O. Saéz (Ed.) *Tecnología educativa. Nuevas tecnologías aplicadas a la educación* (pp. 379-412). Alcoy, Spain: Marfil.
- Florian, L. (2014). What counts as evidence of inclusive education? *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 29(3), 286-294.
- Fullam, M. (2002). El significado del cambio educativo: Un cuarto de siglo de aprendizaje. *Profesorado, revista de currículum y formación del profesorado*, 6 (1-2), 1-14. doi: 10.1080/00405849509543685.
- Gadotti, M. (2007). *La escuela y el maestro: Paulo Freire y la pasión de enseñar*. Sao Paulo, Brasil: Publisher Brasil.

- García, C. H., Serrano, J. L. E., Ruiz, T. B., Sánchez, M. G., González, M., Postigo, A. C., and Catarain, J. (2011). *El liderazgo educativo: proyectos de éxito escolar*. Madrid, Spain: Ministerio de Educación.
- Hopkins, D. (2007). *Every school a Great School. Realizing the potential of system leadership*. New York: MC Graw-Hill education.
- Imbernón, F. (1996). *La formación del profesorado: formar para innovar*. Buenos Aires, Argentina: Magisterio del Río de la Plata.
- Karrera, I. (2008). *La metodología cualitativa crítica como estrategia válida en la resolución de conflictos escolares* (Doctoral theses). Available from Spanis Digital Theses database. Retrieved from <https://www.educacion.es/teseo/mostrarRef.do?ref=562743>
- Karrera, I., Garmendia, M., and Arguiñano, A. (2019). Sinergias entre Inclusión, competencias y Rendimiento Escolar: El caso de la Escuela Pública de Antzuola. *Profesorado, revista de curriculum y formación del profesorado*, 23(1), 84-102. doi:10.30827/profesorado.v23i1.9145
- Kemmis, S. (1994). School Reform in the '90s: Reclaiming Social Justice. Conference: Touchstones of the Socially Just School. Adelaide, Flinders Institute for the Study of Teaching.
- Kemmis, S. (2012). Researching educational praxis: spectator and participant perspectives. *British Educational Research Journal* 38(6), 885-905. doi: 10.1080/01411926.2011.588316
- Krichesky, G. J., and Murillo, F.J. (2011). Las Comunidades Profesionales de Aprendizaje. Una Estrategia de mejora para una nueva Concepción de Escuela. *REICE. Revista Iberoamericana sobre Calidad, Eficacia y Cambio en Educación*, 9(1), 65-83.

- López Melero, M. (2011). Barreras que impiden la escuela inclusiva y algunas estrategias para construir una escuela sin exclusiones. *Innovación Educativa*, 21(1), 37-54.
Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10347/6223>
- Martinic, S. (2001). Conflictos políticos e interacciones comunicativas en las reformas educativas en América Latina. *Revista Iberoamericana de Educación*, 27, 17-33.
Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Sergio_Martinic/publication/28054795_Conflictos_politicos_e_interacciones_comunicativas_en_las_reformas_educativas_en_America_Latina/links/56f13a2e08ae5c367d4a9b1a.pdf
- McCulloch, G. (2004). *Documentary research: In education, history and the social sciences*. New York, UEA. Routledge.
- Parrilla, A. (2007). Inclusive education: A view from Inside. In L. Barton and F. Fletcher (eds), *Policy, Experience and change: cross-cultural reflections on Inclusive Education*. London, England: SpringerBooks.
- Pascual, R. (1988). *La gestión educativa ante la innovación y el cambio*. Madrid, Spain: Narcea.
- Pérez Serrano, G. (2008). *Investigación cualitativa: Retos e Interrogantes*. Madrid, Spain: La Muralla.
- Perrenoud, P. (2011). *Quand l'école prétend préparer à la vie... Des compétences ou d'autres savoirs?*. Paris, France : ESF Editeur.
- Reimers, F. (2000). Educación, desigualdad y opciones de política en América Latina en el siglo XXI. *Revista Latinoamericana de Estudios Educativos*, 30(2), 11-42.
- Sancho, J.M. and Correa, J.M. (2013). Aprender a ser maestra: perplejidades y paradojas. *Cuadernos de pedagogía*, 436, 18-21.

- Sasieta, E., and Etxaniz, P. (2015). He estado pensando y mi cabeza me dice que...
Revista Aula de innovación educativa, 238, 24-28.
- Schulz, K. (2010). *Being Wrong: Adventures in the Margin of Error*. New York, United States of America: Ecco.
- Stoll, L., Bolam, R., McMahon, A., Wallace, M. and Thomas, S. (2006). Professional learning communities: a review of the literature. *Journal of Educational Change*, 7(4), 221-257.
- Tawfik, A. A. (2015). Essential Readings in Problem-Based Learning: Exploring and Extending the Legacy of Howard S. Barrows. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-Based Learning*, 9(2). doi: 10.7771/154150151593
- Valencia Pérez, C and Hernández González, O. (2017). El Diseño Universal para el Aprendizaje, una alternativa para la inclusión educativa en Chile. *Atenas*, 4, 40. 105-120.
- Woods, P. (1987). *La escuela por dentro. La etnografía en la investigación educativa*. Barcelona: Paidós.
- Woods, P. (1989). *La escuela por dentro. La etnografía en la investigación educativa*. Barcelona, Spain: Laertes.
- Zabala, A., and Arnau, L. (2007). La enseñanza de las competencias. *Aula de innovación educativa*, 161, 40-46.

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